

Article

Development Programmes for Primitive Tribal Groups and Their Present Economic Condition—A Case Study of Birhor Tribe in Purulia District

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Abstract

After Independence special protection and safeguard have been taken by the Constitution of India for Scheduled tribes. Apart from this several development schemes have been taken during Five Year Plans. In spite of all these efforts till fifth five year plan some Scheduled tribes lagging behind the other Tribes. So, these under developed tribes identified as Primitive Tribal Groups later as Particularly Vulnerable tribal Groups. Special Central assistance and development schemes have been taken by the Government of India for the development of these particularly vulnerable tribes. Developmental schemes and their implementation/execution and the real situation of such a Particularly vulnerable tribe named Birhor who are reside in Purulia district, West Bengal have been examined in this article.

Key words

Scheduled Tribe, Primitive Tribal Groups (PTGs), Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Group, Tribal Sub-Plan (TSP), Special Central Assistance (SCA), Tribal Cooperative Marketing Development Federation (TRIFED), Development scheme.

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Introduction

After Independence the founding Fathers of Indian constitution made provisions to protect the rights of the Scheduled Tribe community. As per Article 366 of the Constitution of India, Scheduled Tribes are those communities, who are scheduled in accordance with Article 342 of the Constitution. This Article of the Constitution says that only those communities who have been declared as such by the President through an initial public notification or through a subsequent amending Act of Parliament will be considered to be Scheduled Tribes.

The essential characteristics, first laid down by the Lokur Committee, for a community to be identified as Scheduled Tribes are –

- a) indications of primitive traits;
- b) distinctive culture;
- c) shyness of contact with the community at large;
- d) geographical isolation; and
- e) backwardness.

Special provisions have been made in the Constitution for their protection and development.

Development is a process which means movement from a condition towards another, process of gradual unfolding or growth or stage of development. It sums up and designates the most important aspects of changes concerning the wellbeing or uplift the people, in general and it ensures stability cum comfort in the living processes. Development is an active policy which refers to mature economy and self sustaining growth and the related action pattern generate an increase productivity which in course of time will improve the quality of life namely elevating the people from poverty to prosperity and opening up more employment opportunities, setting apart more time leisure time by which their creative art and philosophy can be reflected in finer things, diseases can be checked and ignorance can be removed, if the group is allowed to have a

privileged life style. It is true that many more activities have been extended to all the tribal groups.¹

The main safeguards include promotion of educational and economic interests and their protection from social injustices and all forms of exploitation. The constitution protects the general rights of all Indian citizens to move freely, settle anywhere and acquire property. It also permits the States to make reservation in public services in case of inadequate representation and requiring them to consider their claims in appointments to public service

Development Program during Five Years Plan for Scheduled Tribes and for Primitive Tribal Groups (PTGs)

High priority for the welfare and development of Scheduled Tribes was also taken from the beginning of the First Five Year Plan (1952-57) by the Government of India.

Recognizing their special problems the principles of *Panchsheel* have been adopted in the welfare and development of these communities so as to ensure an understanding of their culture and traditions and an appreciation of the social, psychological and economic problems with which they are faced.² Various commission and committees were also appointed to look after their problems.

In spite of all those effort it has been identified that Tribal groups are at different stages of social, economic and educational development. While some tribal communities have adopted a mainstream way of life, at the other end of the spectrum, there are certain Scheduled Tribes who were still at lowest stage of economic development.

The Dhebar Commission (1960-1961) stated that within Scheduled Tribes there existed an inequality in the rate of development.³ During the fourth Five Year Plan a sub-category was created within Scheduled Tribes to identify groups that

considered to be at a lower level of development. This was created based on the Dhebar Commission report and other studies. This sub-category was named "Primitive tribal group". The features of such a group include a pre-agricultural system of existence, that is practice of hunting and gathering, zero or negative population growth, extremely low level of literacy in comparison with other tribal groups.

Groups that satisfied any one of the criterion were considered as PTG. At the conclusion of the Fifth Five year plan, 52 communities were identified as being a "primitive tribal group", these communities were identified on the basis of recommendations made by the respective state governments.⁴ At the conclusion of the Sixth Five year plan 20 groups were added and 2 more in the Seventh Five year plan, one more group was added in the eighth five-year plan, making a total 75 groups were identified as PTG. Based on pre-agricultural level of technology, low level of literacy, declining or stagnant populations,⁵

In this connection it may be mentioned here that Evan Pritchard characterized primitive societies as those that are small in scale with regard to numbers, territory and the range of social contacts and which by comparison with more advanced society have simple technology, economy and little specialization of social function.⁶

Radfield would like to add further criteria, particularly the absence of literature and hence of any systematic art, science or theology.⁷

75 tribal communities in 17 States and 1 Union Territory of Andaman & Nicobar Island, have been identified and categorized as Primitive Tribal Groups.⁸

In 2006 the government of India proposed to rename "Primary tribal group" as Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Group".⁹ PTG has since been renamed Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Group by the government of India.

From the fifth five year plan onwards special provisions for the development of the Primitive Tribe have been taken.

During Fifth Five Year Plan (1974-78)) for the direct benefit of the development of tribal Tribal Sub- Plan (TSP) scheme had been launched.¹⁰

TSP stipulated that funds of the State and Centre should be quantified on the population proportion basis, with budgetary mechanisms to ensure accountability, non divertability and utilisation for the welfare and development of STs. With this thrust the concept of Tribal Sub-Plan came into action during the Fifth Plan. There has been a substantial increase in the flow of funds for the development of STs under this arrangement, resulting in the expansion of infrastructure facilities and enlargement of coverage of the target groups in the beneficiary oriented programmes. TSP was an umbrella under which all schemes implemented by the States and Central Governments were dovetailed for addressing different needs of the Scheduled Tribes. It was basically an area development programme with focus on tribal under which infrastructural development and family-oriented programmes were undertaken. Family-oriented income-generating schemes were in the sectors of agriculture, horticulture, minor irrigation, soil conservation, animal husbandry, forests, education, cooperatives, fisheries, village and small scale industries and for minimum needs programme. The strategy has been successful in garnering larger flow of funds for the development of Scheduled Tribes from Rs. 759 crore during the Fifth Five Year Plan to about Rs. 16902.66 crore by the end of the Eighth Five Year Plan (1992-97).¹¹

During seventh five year plan for the economic development of SCs and STs, two national level institutions were set up viz., (i) Tribal Cooperative Marketing Development Federation (TRIFED) in 1987 as an apex body for State Tribal Development Cooperative Corporations;¹² and (ii) National Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes Finance and Development Corporation (NSFDC) in 1989. The former was envisaged to provide remunerative price for the Forest and Agriculture Produce of tribals while the latter was intended to

provide credit support for employment generation.

In the Eighth Five Year Plan (1992-97), efforts were intensified to bridge the gap between the levels of development of the STs and those of other sections of the society so that by the turn of the century, these disadvantaged sections of the population could be brought on par with the rest of the society.

Grants are also given to States/UTs, under the article 275(1)¹³ of the Constitution to meet the costs of projects for tribal development and for raising the level of administration of Scheduled Area therein on par with the rest of the State/UT. Part of the funds are utilised for setting up of Residential Schools for providing quality education to tribal students.

Considering the vulnerability of some tribal groups, a Central Sector Scheme was introduced in the year 1998-99 for the all round development of PTGs. The scheme is very flexible, and covers housing, infrastructure development, education, health, land distribution/development, agriculture development, cattle development, social security, insurance, etc.

The National SC & ST Finance Development Corporation - an apex level Organization for both SCs & STs was bifurcated in 2001 allowing the birth of an exclusive working Corporation at national level for ST with an Authorised share capital of Rs.500 crores. Thus, Corporation in collaboration with the State ST Corporations is expected to work as the catalytic agent besides extending both 'forward' and 'backward' linkages of credit and marketing facilities to the micro-level agencies to improve the economic lot of STs.

In addition to the programmes of the Corporation, the nodal Ministry also extended Special Central Assistance (SCA) as an additive to State TSP (Tribal Sub Plan) to promote family based income generation activities to improve the economic conditions of STs. Also the line Ministries of Rural Areas and Employment and Urban Affairs and Employment implement a few nation-wide poverty alleviation programmes viz -

Swarna Jayanti Swa- Rozgar Yojana and Swarna Jayanti Shahari Rozgar Yojana to generate both wage and self employment and income generation opportunities for the benefit of the socially and economically disadvantaged Groups.

In 2008 Ministry of Tribal Affairs, Government of India announce that Most of the PTG groups are small in number, have not attained any significant level of social and economic progress and generally inhabit remote localities having poor infrastructure and administrative support. Therefore, they become the most vulnerable sections among the scheduled tribes and priority is required to be accorded for their protection, checking the declining trend of their population and their development.¹⁴

During 2007-08, comprehensive long term "Conservation-cum-Development (CCD) Plans" for PTGs have been formulated for Eleventh Plan period through baseline surveys conducted by respective State Governments/Union territory.¹⁵ These Plans envisage a synergy between efforts of State Governments and non-governmental organizations. Activities under it may include housing, land distribution, land development, agricultural development, cattle development, construction of link roads, installation of non-conventional sources of energy for lighting purpose, social security including Janshree Beema Yojana or any other innovative activity meant for the socio-economic development approach for the comprehensive socio-economic development of PTGs, more particularly for the PTGs who are nomadic in nature. Whether efforts should be made to bring nomadic PTGs to the settled mode of life, will be carefully addressed. The funds under this scheme would be made available only for those items/activities which are very crucial for the survival, protection and development of PTGs and are not specifically catered to by any other scheme of State or Central Government or by guidelines governing the utilization of funds under Special Central Assistance to Tribal Sub-Plan and Article 275(1) of the Constitution.¹⁶

In West Bengal the fund of Special Central Assistance is mainly utilized for the construction of houses for PTGs and execution of infrastructure development schemes like road, bridge/culvert, Minor Irrigation, Const / Re-const /Rep / Renovation of Ashram and School attached Hostel / School Building in PTGs dominated areas

Special Reference to West Bengal

Primitive Tribal Groups (PTGs)

In West Bengal, three Scheduled tribes communities i.e. Lodha, Birhor and Toto have been declared as PTGs. These PTGs are domiciled in Paschim Medinipur, Purulia, Jalpaiguri and Sagar Block of South 24 Parganas districts i.e. Lodhas in Paschim Medinipur and Sagar Block of South 24 Parganas, Totos in Jalpaiguri and Birhors in Purulia. Presently there are about Birhors, Totos & Lodhas in West Bengal.¹⁷

Primitive Tribal Groups (PTGs) named

Birhor Tribe in Purulia District

Birhor are found in three blocks of Purulia district namely Bagmundi block, Balarampur block and Jhalda I block. Total population of the Birhor tribe in the district is 279 as per Backward Classes Welfare Department.

It has been learnt that most of the Birhors of Purulia migrated from Ranchi, Hazaribagh, Dhanbad of Jharkhand State more than 150 years ago and finally settled in 3 blocks of Purulia like Bagmundi, Jhalda-I and Balarampur. At present they are found living in Bareriya, and Bhupatipalli village in Bagmundi Block, Chhotobakad in Jhalda-I Block and Bersa village under Balarampur Block.¹⁸

Development Schemes for the Birhor

Tribe in Purulia District

Different schemes have been executed from time to time for the Birhors in Purulia district by the Backward Classes Welfare Department which was earlier known as Tribal Welfare Department and thereafter Scheduled Castes and Tribes Welfare Department.

and also to create income generation through various schemes like goatery, piggery, agriculture, Ginger cultivation etc.

Scheduled Caste and Tribes Welfare Department executed the following schemes for the Birhor at Bhupatipally in Purulia district in the year 1975-76.¹⁹(Table No.1)

Table No.1: Schemes for development of Birhors in Bhupatipally, Purulia district

SL No	Name of the Schemes	Unit	Expenditure
01	Construction of Dwelling Houses	20	40000
02	Excavation of Tank	01	12000
03	Reclamation of Land	20 Ha	16700
04	Special repairing of Primary school	01	2000
05	Scheme for semi-mechanised rope making centre	01	7300

During 2006-07 Backward classes Welfare Department made houses for Birhor tribe in Purulia, they built 21 houses for the Birhor Tribe at the cost of 28,87,920, In 2008-09 this Department built 14 houses for the this tribe at the cost of 14,00,000 and in the year 09-10 they made 10 houses for Birhor tribe for Rupees 10,00,000.²⁰

Several other Developmental Schemes taken up for the Birhors of Bagmundih till 2008-09 as per Backward Classes Welfare Department Purulia.²¹(Table 2)

Plate No. 1 : Birhor family members with children at Bhupatipally under Baghmundi Dev. Block in Purulia district

Plate No.2 : Birhor child with his mother at Bhupatipally under Baghmundi Dev. Block in Purulia district

Plate No. 3 : Residential houses of Birhori with their belongings at Bhupatipally under Baghmundi Dev. Block in Purulia district

Plate No. 4 : Livestocks of Birhors at Bareriya under Baghmundi Dev. Block in Purulia district Photos by author.

Table No.2 : Housing schemes

I	Name of the Scheme	Unit	Amount / unit	Total Amount involved
.	Const. of Bhupatipally Pry.Ashram Hostel	1	3,05,220/-	3,05,220/-
.	Low Cost Houses	31	76,596/-	23,74,476/-
.	Low Cost House	21	1,38,000/-	28,87,028/-
	Sanitary Latrine	25	6,000/-	1,50,000/-
	Tube Well	03	84,228/-	2,52,684/-
	Drinking water well	01	39,661/-	39,661/-
	Repair of Drinking water well	03	13,641/-	40,923/-
	Improvement of Road	01	35,000/-	35,000/-
	Goatary Scheme	22	15,000/-	3,30,000/-
	Piggary Scheme	23	22,855/-	5,25,665/-
0	Agriculture and Irrigation Scheme	01	1,48,903/-	1,48,903/-
1	Const. of Boundary wall at Bhupatipally Pry. Ashram Hostel	01	1,38,000/-	1,38,000/-
2	Improvement of Pry. Ashram Hostel	01	2,22,000/-	2,22,000/-
3	Babui Rope Making (@ 12,000/- per unity	15	12,000/-	1,80,000/-
4	Mobile Medical Unit	01	4,00,000/-	4,00,000/-

Several Developmental Schemes taken up for the Birhors of Balarampur till 2008-09 as per Backward Classes Welfare Department, Purulia as follows.²² (Table 3)

Table No. 3 : Schemes for development of Birhors in Balarampur Purulia district

S l.	Name of the Scheme	Unit	Amount / unit	Total Amount involved
1	Low Cost Houses	8	76,596/-	6,12,768/-
2	Sanitary Latrine	8	48,000/-	48,000/-
3	Tube Well	01	28,076/-	28,076/-
4	Drinking water well	01	39,661/-	39,661/-
5	Babui Rope making	05	12,000/-	60,000/-

Several Developmental Schemes taken up for the Birhors of Jhalda-I till 2008-09 as per Backward Classes Welfare Department, Purulia.²³

Table No. 4 : Development schemes in Jhalda

S l.	Name of the Scheme	Unit	Amount / unit	Total Amount involved
1	Low Cost Houses	10	76,596/-	7,65,960/-
2	Sanitary Latrine	10	6,000/-	60,000/-
3	Tube Well	02	28,076/-	56,152/-
4	Drinking water well	01	39,661/-	39,661/-
5	Repair of drinking water well	01	15,000/-	15,000/-
6	Approach Road	01	4,88,000/-	4,88,000/-
7	Approach Road	01	70,000/-	70,000/-
8	Babui Rope Making (@ 12,000/- per unity)	08	12,000/-	96,000/-

Position of Workforce of the Birhor Tribe in Purulia district as follows.²⁴ (Table 5)

Table No. 5 : Position of Workforce of the Birhor Tribe in Purulia district

	Male	Female	Total
Total Population	148	131	279
Total Workers	97	98	195
Agri-Labourers	06	04	10
Cultivators	—	—	—
Day Labourers	64	46	110
Business	—	—	—
Other Services (Rope making, Collection MFP etc.)	27	48	75
Non Workers	51	33	84

Development schemes for the Birhor in the Purulia district for the year 2008-09 as per the Backward Classes Welfare office, Purulia.²⁵

Table No. 6 : Development schemes for Birhor Tribe in Purulia district(2008-09)

S I No	Name of the scheme	Amount	Expenditure	Present status
1	Maintenance and Repair work of low cost houses of Birhor at Bhupatipally under Bagmundi PS	2695000	2502490	Work is almost complete
2	Construction of a community Hall at Bareriya under Bagmundi PS	600000	492874	Do
3	Excavation of tank at Bhupatipally	500000	500000	Complete
4	Health scheme, mobile medical unit for Birhor	400000	400000	Do
5	Construction of field channel 0.5 KM at Bhupatipally	500000	500000	Do
6	Construction of 10 Houses at Bareriya for Birhor	1000000	914889	Do
7	Construction of 02 houses for Birhor at Bersa	200000	00	Running
8	Construction of 01 houses at Mahultarn under Jhalda I PS	100000	00	Do
9	Construction of 01 Houses at Dakai under Jhalda I PS	100000	00	Do

Development schemes for the Birhor in Purulia district for the year 2009-10 as per the Backward Classes Welfare office, Purulia.²⁶

Table No. 7 : Development schemes for the Birhor in Purulia (2009-10)

S I No	Name of the scheme	Amount	Expenditure	Present status
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1	Construction of 10 Houses at Bhupatipally for Birhor	100000 0	465011	
2	Construction of 35 numbers of Latrine at Bhupatipally for Birhor	122500 0	1224175	Complete
3	Construction of 35 numbers of Pen shed at Bhupatipally for Birhor	210000 0	2086854	Do
4	Installation of tranformer at Bhupatipally for Birhor	600000	00	
5	Improvement of Morrum Road from Bersa to Balarampur with culvert under Balarampur PS	120000 0	997764	Complete
6	Sinking and Construction of 03 numbers of Drinking water Tubewell at Bhupatipally for Birhor	225000	186940	Almost completed
7	Construction of Morrum Road at Bhupatipally	100000	96591	Complete
8	Construction of field channel with guard wall at Bhupatipally	750000	715000	Complete
9	Pump house and pump set for agriculture at Bhupatipally	200000	131000	
10	Construction of bathing ghat at Bhupatipally	200000	200000	complete

Discussion

There are some differences in information, regarding development schemes for Birhor in Purulia district for the year 2008-09, provided by the Head Office of Backward Classes Welfare Department, Kolkata and Backward Classes Welfare Department, Purulia. As per the Head office of Backward Classes Welfare Department, Kolkata both infrastructure development schemes and income generating schemes have been taken while as per the Backward Classes Welfare Office Purulia mainly infrastructure development schemes have been taken in the year 2008-09 and 2009-10. However, the main issue is economic development of the Birhor tribe and in reality it have been seen that despite several efforts, of central government and state government, of several decades a small numerically tribe whose total population in this district is only 279, remains still as PTG tribe. Despite several development schemes, the Birhor tribal people belong to Below Poverty Line in this district.

The national poverty line has been fixed at Rs 816 per capita per month for rural areas and Rs 1000 for urban areas.²⁷

The “2002 methodology”, for estimation of Below Poverty Line population, consisted of a survey and measurement system that assigned “scores” to each household on the basis of 13 questions. In addition to ownership of consumer durables and means of production the survey now included questions on food security, sanitation, literacy status, means of livelihood, status of labour including women and children, indebtedness, and migration. The response to each question was scored on a scale of 0 to 4 and thereafter aggregated. Households could score anywhere from 0 to 52. households would be considered as BPL if they scored 33 or less.

Concluding Remarks

Since 2008, there has been vigorous debate and demand within Indian and international policymaking and advocacy circles about revising the mechanisms to identify the “poor” in India, so that social assistance may be better targeted. In August 2009, the government of India made public the Report of the Expert Group that was advising the Ministry of Rural Development on the methodology for conducting the new Below Poverty Line (BPL) Census for the Eleventh Five-Year Plan. Policy of Socio Economic and Caste Census has been introduced in India in 2011.²⁸

State governments are free to establish their own cut-offs for deciding Below Poverty line, based on local criteria and considerations, subject to the Expert Group’s stipulation that the application of such standards should ensure that the total number of poor persons identified in that state/union territory did not exceed the estimates prepared by the Planning Commission by more than 10%. The panchayats were tasked with the responsibility of overseeing the surveys, collecting the data and reviewing it in the light of the cut-off scores established by the state government. Purulia Zilla Parishad published²⁹ BPL list of Rural Household of Purulia on website based on survey made in the year 2005. According to this list 194 Birhor people Of Bagmundi Block belongs to BPL list while only 04 people of Jhalda I block belong to BPL list and no one found in BPL list from Balarampur block. So, as per Purulia Zilla Parishad list some Birhor people remain outside the BPL list. While it has been stated as per the policy of Socio Economic and Caste Census 2011 of Government of India that all PTGs should automatically be included in the list of Below Poverty Line. Due to panchayat election in West Bengal 2013 new list of Below Poverty Line people has not been published.

So, it can be said that efforts made from the beginning of the planned era (1951) through various developmental plans, policies, special strategies and programmes and a definite quantifiable improvement have registered in the socio-economic status of the tribal Specifically the

Birhor tribe in Purulia district. However, the progress made by them could not bring them anywhere nearer to the mainstream society as the gap in their socio-economic status continued to prevail, not only as a matter of prime concern, but also as a task to accomplish during the coming year. Achievements and the persisting gaps found under the three core sectors of education, health and economic development.

So, more care should be taken by the Government, Panchayat bodies for their total development and focus attention should be given for this.

Notes

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